

CO₂-SPICER - CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir

R7.5 Data set and report with results of shallow groundwater monitoring

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November 2023

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1 INTRODUCTION

Shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site, and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development.

In order to assess potential contamination of shallow groundwater by possible CO₂ leakage, a regionally conceived shallow hydrogeological model of the overburden of the storage area was created. The aim was to create a tool for the operational assessment of the risks of pollution migration in shallow aquifers.

In order to establish the groundwater monitoring baseline, periodical water surface surveys in available hydrogeological and monitoring boreholes and selected water wells, including water sampling, were conducted.

The results of this report will be further used in the development of the Site monitoring plan to be prepared in Task 7.6 as the main result V5.

2 SHALLOW GROUNDWATER MODELLING

2.1 Modelling introduction

The workflow of groundwater flow simulation is described in Fig. 2-1.

The objectives of the Task were:

Set up and calibrate groundwater flow model using shallow groundwater monitoring data.

Simulate leaky well - impact of CO₂ dissolution in groundwater – H⁺ ions transport.

The validation of the groundwater flow model was not possible at this stage. Therefore, the calibrated model was used for the predictions in spite of all kinds of uncertainties.

Fig. 2-1: The workflow of shallow groundwater modelling.

2.2 Concept of the groundwater flow model

Defining the concept of the hydraulic model includes:

- defining the relevant physical processes involved in groundwater flow at a given model scale,
- determining the spatial scale of the model, the extent of the model domain,
- description of the relevant components of the system, in particular a geological model with a description of the hydraulic characteristics of the individual rock types or zones;
- description of the relationships between the system components and the surrounding environment of the hydrogeological domain in the form of boundary conditions,
- formulating simplifying assumptions that reduce the complexity of the problem in relation to the modelling objective, enabling quantitative analysis.

2.2.1 Defining relevant physical processes

Considering the objective of the modelling study, the simulation of the shallow groundwater flow system at the Zarosice site and the potential impacts of CO₂ storage, the model was set up to simulate a steady-state groundwater flow in the saturated zone.

The option of solving the problem as transient was discarded due to a number of uncertainties that will be discussed later, as well as the problem statement for which the stationary problem is appropriate.

The study area reveals the scarcity of groundwater in at least two hydrostratigraphic units – Quaternary aquifer and the weathered bedrock. In view of this, the model was therefore conceived as a three-dimensional groundwater flow system.

The simulation software MODFLOW-NWT developed by the USGS (US Geological Survey), was chosen for the modelling solution. The actual modelling was performed in the GMS 10.7 (Aquaveo) pre- and post-processing system.

2.2.2 Determining the spatial scale of the model - the extent of the model domain

In general, the numerical model should (as far as possible) be built within natural hydraulic boundary conditions. However, this requirement is difficult to ensure unless sufficient data are available in the broad vicinity of the area of interest, which itself does not represent the entire hydrogeological structure, and exploration would then be highly unbalanced.

The solution, which was also adopted in this case, is to select hydrological boundaries – local watersheds divides. Thus, at least in the shallowest part of the area of interest, the boundaries are natural and well defined. In this case, no flow boundaries of the second kind were chosen $q=0$.

The range of the model domain is shown in Fig. 2-2. The model boundary is drawn in violet, the river network shows drainage of the model area towards the drainage base in the south-west.

Fig. 2-2: Landuse map (Sentinel-2, ESA).

Basic information on hydrogeological conditions of the area of interest is presented in the Tab. 2-1.

Tab. 2-1: Basic information on hydrogeological conditions of the area of interest

ID-	Name of HG region	Area (km ²)	Type of saturation	Thickness of continuous saturation	Geological unit
32301	Středomoravské Karpaty – severní část	1023.6	local	-	Sediments of Paleogene and Cretaceous of Carpathian System
Lithology	Type of aquifer	Type of permeability	Transmissivity (m ² /s)	Type of mineralisation (g/l)	Chemical type
Claystones, marlstones	Unconfined	Double porous-fracture	Low ≤ 1.10 ⁻⁴	0.3 - 1	Ca-HCO ₃

Concerning geological and hydrogeological conditions, we limit the information to issues closely connected to conceptual modelling. The area of interest belongs to the hydrogeological region 32301 “Středomoravské Karpaty – severní část”.

Geologically the area is built by the sediments of Paleogene and Cretaceous of the Carpathian System (see maps 1: 200 000 in Fig. 2-3 including explanatory notes below). Claystones and marlstones have double porosity (intergranular porosity -fracture porosity) with very low transmissivity below the order of -4 m/s. The bedrock is covered by Quaternary loess (in yellow in Fig. 2-4) and fluvial deposits of low thickness in the narrow bands along the rivers. The Quaternary aquifer is confined.

Fig. 2-3: Geological map 1:200 000 (Czech Geological Survey).

Explanatory notes:

Dominant Lower Oligocene

o-a¹ - Lower Oligocene - ždánice-hustopeče formation: alternation of calcareous clays, claystones and sandstones PG3 1 - N1 to h

Po-a¹ - Lower Oligocene - ždánice-hustopeče formation: mica sandstones (ždánice) pPg3 1 - N1

K - Lower Oligocene – conglomerate with exotic cobbles

Fig. 2-4: Geological map 1:50 000 (Czech Geological Survey).

2.2.3 Geological model of the area, hydrostratigraphic units

Developing a good conceptual model requires compiling detailed information on:
 geological formations – aquifers, aquitards, and aquicludes (DTM, profiles Geofond CGS),

groundwater flow directions – assumption in shallow zone,

hydrological boundaries (recharge, rivers, lakes, wetlands, ...)

hydraulic parameters (hydraulic conductivity, storage coefficient, porosity, ...),

extraction or injection from wells (location, depth, screens, rates),

observations of groundwater head, fluxes, and water quality.

The numerical layers based on geological profiles will be described in the following chapter. The upper boundary of the model was modelled using DTM of the 5th generation (5 m grid). The Quaternary layer represents the first numerical layer; bedrock is modelled in 4 layers enabling gradual decrease in the permeability. The weathered flysch forms the second and the third layer.

2.2.4 Discretization of the model

The discretization is performed in five numerical layers, corresponding to the geologically determined layers described in the previous subchapter. The model domain is irregular in shape with an approximate areal extent of 12,3 x 11,6 m. The model grid is regular with cell sizes 20 m. The total number of cells in grid is 1 784 250.

The model network can be seen in Fig. 2-5 in 3-dimensional view from the South and in Fig. 2-6 in in 3-dimensional view from the North. The figures are vertically exaggerated.

Fig. 2-5: Model domain discretization - network in 3D, view from the South.

Fig. 2-6: Model domain discretization - network in 3D, view from the North.

2.3 Shallow groundwater flow model calibration

The calibration of a groundwater flow model is a time-consuming process of adjusting the input parameters of a numerical model so that the measured and simulated quantities, in the case of a hydraulic model, groundwater levels and fluxes, if available, match each other to the maximum extent possible. If measurements or independent variables of the water balance components (effective infiltration - recharge, drainage by surface recipients, springs or artificial drains, etc.) are not available, then the calibration is ambiguous (so-called nonunique).

As mentioned above, the model is built as a steady state model, which in any case represents the first stage of numerical model development, and given the level of uncertainty and the modelling objective, the steady state model is an adequate tool for making predictions under the desired scenarios.

The first step is to select the so-called calibration targets. The project partner CGS provided a database of monitoring levels in shallow wells. Groundwater levels were repeatedly measured in eight shallow wells to assess groundwater regime during a hydrological year. The groundwater regime appears to be very stable.

In addition to the data set above given, we received data on 205 groundwater level measurements over decades (CGS Geofond). As the measurements were done under various hydrological conditions at different periods, they need to be handled with caution (low reliability). No flux measurements were available for the calibration process.

The results of calibration are presented in Tab. 2-2 in the form of simulated heads and residuals - difference between simulated and observed groundwater levels (1st numerical layer).

Tab. 2-2: Calibration targets, groundwater levels measurements (CGS)

Name	Type	Layer	Allowed error (m)	Simulated head (m a.s.l.)	Residual (m)
ZA001	obs. pt	1	1	202.08	-1.88
ZA002	obs. pt	1	1	212.23	0.27
ZA006	obs. pt	1	1	210.01	-0.78
ZA007	obs. pt	1	1	210.53	0.11
ZA009	obs. pt	1	1	208.67	0.13
ZA010	obs. pt	1	1	213.31	-0.22
ZA011	obs. pt	1	1	192.45	0.69
ZA012	obs. pt	1	1	216.77	-2.43

The level of calibration was assessed by comparing the simulated groundwater levels with the groundwater levels measured throughout the area of interest. The success of the calibration is assessed by the following statistical variables:

- average error (residual) $ME = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_m - h_s)_i$,

- mean absolute error (residual) $MAE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |h_m - h_s|_i$,
- root mean squared residual $RMS = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (h_m - h_s)_i^2}$ and
- normalized RMS $RN = \frac{RMS}{H_{\max} - H_{\min}}$,

where h_m is the measured groundwater level (piezometric level) at the observation object, h_s is the simulated groundwater level (p.u.) at the same object, n is the total number of objects used in the model calibration, and H_{\max} and H_{\min} represent the maximum and minimum of measured groundwater levels (p.u.), respectively.

The calibration was completed with mean absolute error $MAE = 2.35$ m and root mean squared residual $RMS = 3.65$ m. All statistical errors are presented in Fig. 2-8.

Properties	Notes
Property	Value
Mean Residual (Head)	-0,91
Mean Absolute Residual (Head)	2,35
Root Mean Squared Residual (Head)	3,65
Mean Residual (Flow)	0,00
Absolute Residual (Flow)	0,00
Root Mean Squared Residual (Flow)	0,00
Mean Weighted Residual (Head+Flow)	0,00
Mean Absolute Weighted Residual (Head+Flow)	0,00
Root Mean Squared Weighted Residual (Head+Flow)	0,00
Sum of Squared Weighted Residual (Head+Flow)	0,00
Displayed Precision	2
* For more information on weighted residuals, see the wiki help page.	

Fig. 2-8: Statistical errors of the model calibration.

The calibrated parameters were the hydraulic conductivities of all model layers and the recharge from precipitation to the quaternary aquifer. The calibration was done using PEST code (Parameter ESTimation) – automatic calibration ([Software | PEST \(pesthompage.org\)](http://Software | PEST (pesthompage.org))). PEST refers to a suite of software that is an essential complement to numerical simulation when undertaken to serve the decision-support imperatives of:

- quantifying the uncertainties of decision-critical predictions; and
- reducing these uncertainties as much as available data allows.

The comparison between the computed (simulated) and observed groundwater levels at all calibration targets can be seen in Fig. 2-9. When there is absolute agreement, the points form a straight line. It can be seen from the figure that the level of agreement is very good and there is no trend error. The points are randomly distributed around the straight line, as evidenced by the statistical error.

As groundwater levels were measured over a long period (decades) their reliability is low. In this view point the calibration is acceptable; moreover, the residuals are randomly distributed along the line (positive).

Fig. 2-9: Comparison of the computed (simulated) and observed groundwater levels.

The first numerical layer was calibrated within zones defined by pedological map, and other layers were calibrated as homogeneous throughout the model domain. The result of calibration is presented in Fig. 2-10 and Tab. 2-3.

Fig. 2-10: Calibrated hydraulic conductivities in the first numerical layer.

Tab. 2-3: Calibrated parameters

Calibrated parameters	Value
Hydraulic conductivity – layer 1 (m/s)	E-4 to E-7
Hydraulic conductivity – layer 2 (m/s)	E-6
Hydraulic conductivity – layer 3 - 5 (m/s)	E-7 – E-8
Recharge – fluvial quaternary deposits (mm/year)	69
Recharge – Carpathian flysch deposits (mm/year)	10

It is important to note that without flux measurements the calibration is non-unique.

2.4 Shallow groundwater model results

The results of the shallow groundwater flow model will be presented in the following text in the form of groundwater level contours for individual layers in 3D (Fig. 2-11) and in 2D (Fig. 2-12, Fig. 2-13).

Fig. 2-11: Shallow groundwater level contours in model domain.

Fig. 2-12: Shallow groundwater level contours in the 1st numerical layer (Quaternary).

Tab. 2-4: Water budget of the shallow groundwater flow model

Sources/Sinks	Flow in (m ³ /day)	Flow out (m ³ /day)
Constant head	12 825,8	-15 937,7
Drains	0.0	-1140.4
Recharge	4251.9	0.0
Total Source/Sink	17 077.7	-17 078.1
Total flow	17 077.7	-17 078.1
Summary	In - Out	% difference
Sources/Sinks	-0.421	-0.002
Total	-0.421	-0.002

2.5 Solute transport modelling

One of the objectives of the modelling study was to analyse the risk of CO₂ leakage through the monitoring well. Since the software used only allows the simulation of single phase fluid flow, leakage was simulated through H⁺ ions that would be hydrochemically generated after the release of gaseous CO₂ into groundwater. The transport was simulated as advective-dispersive since reactive transport is not expected in the case of H⁺ ions.

Transport was simulated as transient in a stationary flow field, the simulation period was 20 years.

Taking into account the objective of the study, a conservative scenario was chosen: a CO₂ leaky well with a constant source of H⁺ ions of 7.94.10⁻⁶ mol/L. The initial concentration and the concentration in the precipitation were given 3.16.10⁻⁸ mol/l. The information about the pollution source is presented in Table 2-5.

Tab. 2-5: Source of pollution – leaky borehole

Name	X_JTSK	Y_JTSK	X_S42	Y_S42	Z (m a. s.l.)	Depth (m)	Comment
ZA3	1179544.79	573502.54	5437240.90	644202.09	219.28	1923.00	planned monitoring well into the gas cap

Transport modelling was performed in MT3DMS and particle tracking in MODPATH. The results of transport modelling in MT3DMS are presented in Fig. 2-14.

Fig. 2-14: Transport modelling of H⁺ ions, simulation of 20 years of transport in steady state flow field, the length of plume in the first layer 715 m, in the fifth layer 180 m.

The solute transport modelling proved the low mobility of solutes in low permeable rock environment. The only vulnerable layer is Quaternary layer where the solutes are transported towards the closest drainage base – stream in the distance of 715 m. In the flysch rock mass the transport path did not exceed 180 m from the borehole.

Fig. 2-15 shows the same results in 2D in the first layer. On the right there are results of particle tracking from the monitoring borehole. It is obvious that the impact of potential leakage is very local.

Fig. 2-15: Transport modelling results, H⁺ ions plume after 20 years (left), particle tracking in steady state flow field (right) in the first Quaternary layer (the length of plume in the first layer 715 m).

2.6 Conclusions of the shallow groundwater modelling

The groundwater flow and solute transport model was built and calibrated in the model domain at natural hydrological boundaries (catchment). The modelling study supports the expectation of very low permeable hydrogeological structures with low recharge. The majority of groundwater flow is located within narrow alluvial deposits and the weathered zone of the Carpathian flysch; the flow directions are consistent with the terrain.

The simulation of potential leakage from the monitoring borehole of the storage reservoir impacted only very locally the shallow zone. Thus, the potential environmental impact of leakage would be very low.

3 DIPOLE ELECTROMAGNETIC PROFILING

Geophysical survey using dipole electromagnetic profiling (DEMP) within the Žarošice site was performed in three individual field sessions (26-Oct, 17-Nov and 18-Nov 2021).

Main aim of this workflow is:

- (i) to better identify or predict possible preferential pathways for CO₂ degassing above the deposit,
- (ii) to assess the relationship between results of DEMP and direct CO₂ surveys,
- (iii) to design effective infrastructure for reasonable monitoring of possible CO₂ leakages.

Total of ca. 17 profiles with a variable length of 600–1,700 m was measured on the site covering over 1.2 km² (rectangle ca. 900 × 1,500 m). Over 4,400 values of apparent conductivity were measured. Interpolated map of apparent conductivities is presented in Fig. 3-1. Electromagnetic survey showed three main zones characterized as relatively isometric low-conductivity anomalies (<45 mS.m⁻¹) with 300–400 m in diameter. They are located in the northernmost part of the site (local name *Maliny*) and within the southern part near *Díly za dvorem* and *Petrovec* (Fig. 3-1). The anomalies are separated from each other by relatively high-conductivity domains with values exceeding 60 mS.m⁻¹. The conductive zone in the northern part of the territory has a linear character and stretches in the W–E direction in length of over 700 m. The measured conductivities higher than 70 mS.m⁻¹ are represented by two zones – a relatively smaller isometric domain north of *Petrovec* (over 50 m wide in diameter) and a larger zone (ca. 200 m) in the southernmost tip of the surveyed area.

In spite of strong negative correlation between conductivity and altitude, the areas of conductive domains need to be further analyzed from the point of view of occurrence of potential preferential pathways for CO₂ flux. This can be done by comparison of the identified zones with results of CO₂ site monitoring at the Žarošice site.

Fig. 3-1: Results of ground-based dipole electromagnetic profiling performed at the Zar-3 site. The survey showed three main zones characterized as relatively isometric low-conductivity anomalies (<45 mS.m⁻¹) with 300–400 m in diameter.

4 SHALLOW GROUNDWATER MONITORING

The shallow groundwater monitoring is essential for both understanding the shallow groundwater regime on the site, and establishing a baseline for subsequent monitoring of groundwater quality in later stages of site development. This Task is executed by CGS and VSB.

From 2021 to 2023, the shallow hydrogeological monitoring campaigns were performed by CGS in March, June, October and December to cover all seasons of the year. In 2023, the campaigns were performed in March and October only. The groundwater level (m), spring yield (l/s), electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$), pH (-) and water temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) have been monitored. From the beginning, 19 monitoring points/objects (Fig. 4-1) have been monitored. Those are e.g. shallow wells, boreholes and springs. Unfortunately, access to 3 original monitoring points was not possible in 2022 nor in 2023 due to various reasons, such as new fence construction or the frozen borehole lid in winter.

Fig. 4-1: Position of 19 original groundwater monitoring points near the Zar-3 site. Access to 3 monitoring points (labelled in red) was not possible in 2022 nor in 2023.

4.1 Results of shallow groundwater monitoring

Groundwater level measurements were performed in five boreholes and five wells. Measurements were made with the water-level indicator cable with ca. 1 cm accuracy. Results of groundwater level are shown in Fig. 4-2 and Tab 4-1.

Fig. 4-2: Results of groundwater level measurements (m) in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2022.

Tab. 4-1: Dataset of groundwater level measurements (m) in monitored objects on the site in 2021 and 2022

	1.3.	1.6.	1.10.	22.12.	29.3.	23.6.	17.10.	15.12.	27.3.	6.10.
	2021				2022				2023	
ZA001	-10.53	-10.54	-10.10	-10.40	-10.50	-10.75	-10.83	-10.91	-10.99	-10.85
ZA002	-6.62	-6.55	-6.68	-6.69	-6.83	-6.80	-6.95	-6.96	-6.92	-7.03
ZA004	-1.53	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA005	-2.14	-2.30	-2.31	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA006	-2.50	-2.28	-2.28	-2.24	-2.23	-2.43	-2.67	-2.79	-2.80	-2.84
ZA007	-1.31	-1.65	-1.67	-1.55	-1.54	-	-	-	-1.44	-2.26
ZA009	-5.51	-9.70	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA010	-1.24	-1.32	-1.50	-1.35	-1.29	-1.61	-1.83	-1.77	-6.96	-2.40
ZA011	-3.06	-3.22	-3.51	-3.42	-3.48	-3.60	-3.89	-3.64	-6.96	-3.82
ZA012	-1.27	-1.31	-1.30	-1.30	-1.31	-1.32	-1.35	-1.32	-1.35	-1.38
ZA013	-0.50	-0.41	-0.45	-0.43	-0.45	-0.51	-0.54	-0.57	-0.50	-0.62
ZA014	-3.24	-3.26	-3.27	-3.31	-3.30	-3.26	-3.40	-3.39	-3.36	-3.38
ZA016	-4.65	-5.39	-5.73	-5.73	-5.40	-5.76	-6.07	-6.17	-6.28	-6.33

Spring yield was monitored in two cases. The water flowing out of the spring was collected in a container – the time taken to fill the container was measured and the yield in litres per second determined. Results of spring yield are shown in Fig. 4-3 and Tab 4-2.

Fig. 4-3: Spring yields (litres /sec) of monitored objects ZA008 and ZA019 measured from 2021 to 2023.

Tab. 4-2: Dataset of spring yields (litres/sec) of monitored objects ZA008 and ZA019 measured from 2021 to 2023

	1.3.	1.6.	1.10.	22.12.	29.3.	23.6.	17.10.	15.12.	27.3.	6.10.
	2021				2022				2023	
ZA008	0.116	0.125	0.052	0.085	0.078	0.017	-	0.035	0.030	-
ZA019	0.128	0.123	0.101	0.117	0.114	0.100	0.087	0.087	0.106	0.083

The conductivity of a groundwater is highly dependent on the concentration of dissolved salts and other chemical species that ionize in the solution. Electrical conductivity of water samples is used as an indicator of how salt-free, ion-free, or impurity-free the sample is; the purer the water, the lower the conductivity and vice versa. Conductivity measurements in water are usually reported as specific conductance, relative to the conductivity of pure water at 25 °C. An EC meter capable of providing such values was used to measure water conductivity at Zar-3 (Fig. 4-4, Tab. 4-3).

Fig. 4-4: Results of water electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) measurements in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023.

Tab. 4-3: Dataset of water electrical conductivity ($\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$) measurements in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023

	1.3.	1.6.	1.10.	22.12.	29.3.	23.6.	17.10.	15.12.	27.3.	6.10.
	2021				2022				2023	
ZA001	1112	1585	1090	1377	1193	1233	1263	1186	1169	1148
ZA002	1121	2071	1471	1557	2195	2121	853	1121	2113	2839
ZA003	970	959	913	941	940	910	917	1133	982	886
ZA004	1467	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA005	2158	1958	1948	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA006	1203	2160	1045	-	2420	2199	2127	2151	2378	1846
ZA007	869	1240	980	1755	1757	-	-	1791	1800	1435
ZA008	1592	1525	1500	1464	1439	1424	-	1420	1475	-
ZA009	630	590	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA010	1357	1355	1331	1351	1307	1290	1264	1250	1250	-
ZA011	2085	2168	2051	2054	1970	0	1766	1885	1784	1645
ZA012	2043	1640	822	1939	2052	1885	2002	2097	2126	1603
ZA013	1238	1233	1180	1290	1263	1006	1071	1221	1227	856
ZA014	588	1132	1147	1168	1156	1175	1147	1132	1135	1165
ZA015	1505	1329	1303	1389	1273	1149	631	1382	1345	1172
ZA016	2340	2200	1944	1860	1920	1893	1808	1793	1795	1864
ZA017	1590	1525	1527	1634	1643	1573	1392	1653	1955	1435
ZA018	-	1169	1160	-	-	1143	1127	-	-	1206
ZA019	1218	1177	1188	1181	1170	1200	1094	1156	1205	1130

The *pH* indicates the concentration of hydrogen ions in the solution. At 25 °C, solutions with a *pH* less than 7 are acidic, and solutions with a *pH* above 7 are basic. Solutions with a *pH* of 7 at this temperature are neutral (e.g. pure water). The measurement results are shown in Fig. 4-5.

Fig. 4-5: Measured water pH (-) in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023.

Tab. 4-4: Dataset of water pH (-) measured in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023

	1.3.	1.6.	1.10.	22.12.	29.3.	23.6.	17.10.	15.12.	27.3.	6.10.
	2021				2022				2023	
ZA001	7.54	7.30	7.33	7.33	7.32	7.40	7.29	7.12	7.10	7.39
ZA002	7.36	7.12	6.95	7.44	7.19	7.17	7.11	8.19	7.57	7.30
ZA003	7.53	7.32	7.12	7.55	7.39	7.45	7.40	6.97	6.92	7.61
ZA004	7.93	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA005	7.86	7.86	7.37	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA006	7.22	7.21	7.62	-	6.99	7.11	7.16	7.39	6.76	7.45
ZA007	7.56	8.19	8.18	7.38	7.36	-	-	7.53	7.65	7.40
ZA008	7.18	6.68	7.02	7.12	7.17	7.15	-	6.69	6.73	-
ZA009	8.56	8.63	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
ZA010	9.57	9.42	9.32	9.22	9.30	9.44	9.71	9.71	9.39	-
ZA011	7.91	7.30	7.06	7.86	7.60	-	7.52	7.83	7.68	7.37
ZA012	7.62	7.60	8.41	7.60	7.63	7.94	8.15	7.77	7.60	8.15
ZA013	7.31	7.39	8.01	7.37	7.52	8.58	8.63	7.49	7.75	9.36
ZA014	7.76	7.51	7.10	7.65	7.87	7.62	7.61	7.90	8.16	7.66
ZA015	7.91	8.03	8.13	8.15	8.23	8.17	8.64	7.86	7.90	8.79
ZA016	7.25	6.94	6.91	7.13	7.20	7.08	6.95	6.98	7.12	7.07
ZA017	7.17	7.06	7.05	7.20	7.27	7.30	7.39	6.82	6.69	8.15
ZA018	-	7.18	7.34	-	-	7.44	7.47	-	-	7.66
ZA019	7.22	7.06	7.09	7.23	7.19	7.30	7.32	6.74	6.67	7.46

The water temperature reflects the depth of its circulation; water with a shallow circulation is more reflective to changes in air temperature throughout the year and vice versa. The measurement results are shown in Fig. 4-6.

Fig. 4-6: Water temperature (°C) in monitored objects on the site in from 2021 to 2023.

Tab. 4-5: Dataset of temperature (°C) measured in monitored objects on the site from 2021 to 2023

	1.3.	1.6.	1.10.	22.12.	29.3.	23.6.	17.10.	15.12.	27.3.	6.10.	
	2021				2022				2023		
ZA001	11.3	14.1	13.7	12.6	14.6	16.5	12.6	12.0	12.3	12.8	
ZA002	11.2	13.4	13.3	11.5	12.6	15.1	12.2	10.5	10.9	12.1	
ZA003	5.5	11.7	15.4	5.6	9.0	15.0	12.8	8.1	9.4	13.9	
ZA004	5.4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
ZA005	8.0	14.4	15.6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
ZA006	-	13.1	16.8	-	10.6	14.9	13.1	9.3	9.2	14.2	
ZA007	-	14.1	14.1	9.4	11.7	-	12.1	9.0	8.3	13.9	
ZA008	7.7	11.1	12.9	8.7	9.2	13.7	-	9.4	8.8	-	
ZA009	11.0	14.0	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	
ZA010	10.5	14.0	14.6	10.0	11.6	13.3	13.5	10.8	9.4	-	
ZA011	10.8	14.3	15.6	11.3	11.6	-	14.0	11.8	10.1	14.3	
ZA012	9.6	16.5	18.1	10.7	11.7	20.0	15.8	11.2	9.4	18.1	
ZA013	8.0	16.0	13.7	9.0	13.3	19.7	11.7	8.4	8.4	13.2	
ZA014	9.9	14.4	15.4	9.1	11.1	12.2	12.5	10.6	7.9	12.7	
ZA015	8.3	14.1	12.7	3.3	11.7	19.6	14.8	2.3	7.2	12.2	
ZA016	10.6	12.2	14.0	11.8	12.4	15.1	11.3	10.9	10.7	11.3	
ZA017	7.2	10.6	13.3	9.7	9.9	19.9	13.2	8.9	8.4	13.8	
ZA018	-	11.8	12.5	-	-	14.1	11.9	-	-	12.7	
ZA019	9.5	11.7	11.1	9.2	11.3	11.5	10.6	9.9	9.7	11.5	

The measured water temperatures reflect the effect of seasonal variations in air temperature and the depth of water circulation. Waters with deeper circulation have less difference between the temperature values measured in the warmer and colder parts of the year than waters with circulation closer to the surface.

4.2 Conclusions of shallow groundwater monitoring

The results of the individual measurements reflect the natural conditions in the area of interest, except for minor deviations that can be attributed to inaccuracies and errors.

- The water temperature and groundwater level reflect the effect of seasonal variations (temperature) and the depth of water circulation.

- Water with deeper circulation has more stable temperature during different season of the year (and vice versa)
- The preliminary results indicate no anomalies were observed in area (nor in water temperature and level, spring yields, conductivity or pH)
- All data measured from 2021 to 2023 correspond to the expected natural conditions typical for wider region of the area of interest.

All the determined values were stored in the database managed by CGS. Due to the regular three-year monitoring, basic comparative values for individual parameters are available. The individual objects used for the shallow groundwater monitoring can be easily accessed and re-used in the future for possible comparative measurements. The possible impact of the CO₂ injection and storage can thus be monitored.

This report is a result of the CO₂-SPICER project
(CO₂ Storage Pilot In a CarbonatE Reservoir) - project No: TO01000112.

The CO₂-SPICER project benefits from a €2.32 mil. grant
from Norway and Technology Agency of the Czech Republic.

More information about the project can be found at
co2-spicer.geology.cz.

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